

CREATION OF ONLINE IDENTITY: THE ROLE OF SPORTS AUTHORITY OF INDIA (SAI) WEBSITE

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Abstract

Sports Authority of India (SAI) is an organization responsible for sports promotion throughout India. E-governance initiatives in SAI started in 2014 with the creation of its website. In this paper, the focus would be on examining how websites help in creating an online identity of SAI and its users. For analyzing the issue in detail, Actor Network Theory (ANT) has been chosen. ANT recognizes the importance of interaction between technological and social actors and the process that mutually shapes the two. It takes into consideration how actors are enrolled in a network, and how these actors combine to form a whole network and achieve its stability. The primary aim of this paper is to stress the role of websites in developing user-administrator interactions.

Keywords: Actor Network Theory (ANT); Administrator-User Interactions; E-Governance; Information and Communication Technology (ICT); Sports Authority of India (SAI).

INTRODUCTION

Today internet has become a focal point for almost all public and private organizations. Individuals in India using the internet have grown to 34.4^a per 100 people³. The government of every nation is trying to use Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) to their advantage by improving their internal functioning and relationship with citizens (Dawes et al., 1999; Garson, 2004; Prabhu, 2012; Suri & Sushil, 2017). This move to make public services available using ICTs to all the intended users is called e-governance. The Administrative Reform Commission (ARC) defines e-Governance as “the use by government agencies of Information Technologies (such as Wide Area Networks, the Internet and mobile computing) that have the ability to transform relations with citizens, businesses, and various arms of government resulting in better delivery of government services to citizens, improved interactions with business and industry, citizen empowerment through access to information, or more efficient government management” (ARC, 2008, p. ii & iii).

E-governance can be understood as a socio-technical system. It includes various actors interacting with each other; they may be social, technical, or political. It is necessary to understand all these actors and it is here that Actor Network Theory (ANT) plays a crucial role. ANT uses single terminology for both social and technical actors without favouring one over the other (Lamoure, 2003). It takes into consideration how actors are enrolled in a network, how these actors combine to form a whole network and achieve its stability. Social and technical actors mutually contribute to forming the information networks.

This gamut of actions and actors and networks formed by them need to be observed on the website of the Sports Authority of India (SAI). SAI is a foundation stone for building sports infrastructure in India. Though there is rapid development in field of sports, but this discipline has not been given due consideration in the academic world. Moreover, the research activities in this field are mainly limited to sports management, physiology of exercise, sports psychology, corporate governance in sports, and motor learning (Sharma, 1994). The importance of sports can be seen from the fact that the number of countries participating in the Olympics are more than the number of countries participating in the United Nations (UN). SAI is responsible for the promotion of sports in India. Many of the leading sportspersons from India are the product of this organization. It spots the talent and nurtures them. This makes the organization crucial for evaluation.

Website is seen as the initial step towards achieving e-governance. SAI build its website in 2014 that was revamped recently in July 2021⁴. The website can be seen as a link among different actors such as government, businesses, and citizens. In this research, attempt is made to showcase that website is not only the place to put information online but it also helps in creating the online identity of both the user and the organization.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This research paper addresses the issue of identification.

- How websites create an online identity for the user
- How the website interacts with users to create the online existence of the organization (i.e., Sports Authority of India)

E-Governance

E-Governance has been defined by many scholars in different ways. Dawes (2008, p. S36), for example, defines it as: "E-governance comprises the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) to support public services, government administration, democratic processes, and relationships among citizens, civil society, the private sector, and the state." E-governance is not simply governance with electronic medium, there is more to it. Further, "e-Governance is the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in government in ways that either:

- (1) Alter governance structures or processes in ways that are not feasible without ICT and/or
- (2) Create new governance structures or processes that were heretofore not possible without ICT and/or
- (3) Reify heretofore theoretical ideas or issues in normative governance" (Bannister & Connolly, 2012, p. 11).

It is Bannister and Connolly's definition that is most suited to this study, as it will help to observe clear changes in the sports governance. So far, no study has been found on SAI's e-governance implementation. But area of e-governance is well researched in Indian scenario. To

give an example, research was conducted to study e-governance in Secretariat (Banglore, Karnataka). Implementation of e-governance in secretariat was named as 'Sachivalaya Vahini'. Secretariat had 40 departments with 6000 staff catering in it. To provide to their needs National Information Centre (NIS) designed, developed, and implemented a suite of software packages in all departments. One such software was 'Kadatha- File Monitoring System'. It helped in monitoring, tracking and speedy disposal of files (Prabhu, 2012). This example illustrates that ICT helped in changing the governance process as now concerned persons could know the status of their file, for instance, where the file is pending and for what reasons.

There are many applications of ICTs prevalent in government organizations, but nothing is more prominent than websites. A website is seen as a comprehensive point of access for various electronic delivery of public services (Gant et al., 2002). They have the potential to change the way interactions take place among various stakeholders like citizens, and businesses. There are various advantages of using websites, such as; information can be accessed quickly and at a lower cost (Newman, 2007). But there is another side to it that is putting information online may lead to problems of privacy and confidentiality. These problems need to be taken care of so that citizens can have full trust in government organization's websites.

Sports Authority of India (Sai) & Its Website

SAI was created in 1984 to give special focus on sports. It was set up by the resolution of the Department of Sports, with the objective of promotion of Sports and Games. Its major role was to develop sports infrastructure in various parts of the country and prepare sports talent for international participation. It is also responsible for maintaining and utilizing the Stadia, which were constructed/renovated for the IX Asian Games held in New Delhi in 1982.

It is responsible for searching for talent at micro level and nurturing them towards excellence. Giving the players proper training and providing them with international exposure. They provide players with high standard scientific and sports equipment. Trained and well-experienced coaches measure players' performance through a scientific evaluation system. Most of the leading sports personalities in our country are the product of this organization. SAI is a vast organization. It has six regional and three sub-centers, along with the head office. It also has two academic divisions.

At present, the jurisdiction of sports comes under the Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports. SAI ventured into e-governance practices in 2014 by developing its own website that have been recently updated in July 2021⁵. In 2014, SAI made its website in pursuance of the Electronic Delivery of Services Bill. The website provides information on organization of SAI, budget & finance, schemes launched by it, and various news or updates related to the organization. It is a primary gateway for providing information regarding schemes, stadia, tenders, job opportunities, etc., to athletes, coaches, and the public. It can be accessed 24 hours a day wherever the internet is available. These nuances construct an online identity of the organization. The content of website is determined by various factors, for example, the sports culture of India. In India the last sports policy came in the year 2001, i.e., National Sports Policy, 2001. The major goals of the new policy were to promote mass sports and the

achievement of excellence at national and international level (excellence-level sports). A move was made to shift sports from state list to concurrent list, so that centre can form policies and fund the sports organizations for promotion of sports. Policy also proposed to frame by-laws and models to be followed by the Indian sports federation, while respecting the Olympic Charter. A National Sports Development Fund had been created with initial funding from the Union government. The last concrete development in the sports field was the introduction of the National Sports Development Code, 2011. This bill focused on initiating good governance practices within sports organizations in India. This aim was achieved through e-governance. The website was launched as a part of e-governance initiatives. Cantoni and Tardini (2006) view websites as technological and communication tools that help in creating an organization's online identity. The website of SAI can be seen as a network of social and technological actors (Mitev, 2009). It includes actors like administrators, users, the internet, software, etc. whose agenda is to provide online sports-related services to interested stakeholders.

Online Identity

Today we live in a networked society that has led to an increase in number of different identities. The organizations recreate their identity on internet to build their online identity. Their online identity may differ from their offline identity or print media identity, as it is fluid and can be changed rapidly (Schafer, 2010). But this doesn't mean that there is hard line separating the online and offline identity, rather it is just the difference of space in which they are created. Online identity is determined by various factors such as information content, feedback, security, ease of contact with the administrators, basically interconnectivity and interactivity, since the website handles interactive communication with the customers (Kotler et al., 2008; Fritz, 2007; Nandan, 2005; Ranganathan & Ganapathy, 2002; Rossmann, 2010; Sassen, 2004).

There is various research focusing on the issue of identity (Adam et al., 2006; Bose et al., 2009; Kubicek, 2010). Rissanen (2010) studies the diffusion of the Finnish Electronic Identity Card and how it is different from older ID cards. Similarly, the role of these eIDs is to create a new identity for the person. eID becomes an artifact with multiple roles attached to it (Hedstrom et al., 2015).

For searching sports information online, citizens prefer trusted government websites over some private websites (Sillence, Briggs, Harris, & Fishwick, 2007). When consumers interact with the online interface of an organization, they create their online identity (Schau & Muniz, 2002). For example- when we use Microsoft software, it asks for our identification details, after we fill our specifics, we create our own identity through which that software recognizes us. Therefore, our identity is influenced by these interfaces. Similarly, we as consumers also influence the identity of the organization we interact. Thus, it is a two-way process.

Theoretical Framework

Success of e-governance depends on various actors. Any e-governance project involves appropriate hardware and corresponding system software; networking of the hardware involves—both the Internet and Intranet environment; and application software along with

appropriate database management software. Along with these, we have human actors participating in the process of e-governance and influencing it. It is required to develop deeper understanding about the complex interplay of situation, actors, and processes in the e-governance context (Suri & Sushil, 2017). To understand the dynamic nature of e-governance in SAI we need to study both human and non-human actors in play and how both interact with each other. Human actors may include planners, implementers as well as beneficiaries. Therefore, the theoretical framework chosen for this study is Actor-Network Theory (ANT).

ANT recognizes the importance of interaction between technology and organization and the process that mutually shapes the two. It focuses on the “dynamic interaction between the two that shapes the ongoing configuration of technology and organization” (Cordella and Shaikh, 2006, p.7). According to Actor-Network Theory (ANT), humans are not the only actors that compose the social sphere, since non-human actors are also part of it (Latour, 2005). Therefore, ANT’s contribution to social theory is in the recognition that social actors and social relationships do not exist without non-human actors (Whittle & Spicer, 2008). Law (1992) also corroborates this issue by emphasizing that social is not simply human related. Material aspects are not just tools to be used to accomplish tasks but are also constitutive of both activities and identities (Orlikowski & Scott, 2008). Therefore, one cannot assume the SAI website as a neutral entity but it needed to be understood as output of the “interaction of heterogeneous elements that are shaped and assimilated into an open-ended network” (Law, 1990, p.107).

The actor as an entity does not embody action rather action is produced due to relational effect when actors interact with other actors. Actors both influence and get influenced by the networks. And stabilization of these networks occurs when there is an alignment among different actors (Cordella and Shaikh, 2006). Actors while interacting within the networks negotiate their forces in process of translation. Translation can be understood as negotiation, acts, force, or calculation, which an actor takes on behalf of another actor. When actors translate each other, they try to enroll the other to support or believe in them (Latour, 1987). Latour and Woolgar (1986) describes, “A network (is) a set of positions within which an object... has meaning, it is clear that the facticity of an object is relative only to a particular network or networks.” A key to building these networks is micro processing or microanalysis of facts. It is crucial to understand these complex shifts between micro and macro levels because it is here that we can trace the change occurring in the organization or the society. These changes can help us in indicating where we need to focus our effort.

ANT as an approach can have various benefits both conceptually and practically. It appreciates the complexity and fluidity of reality, which also includes complexity of the organization (SAI). It helps to understand how different realities are enacted by different actors which further helps to conceptualize how the dynamic relationship among actors are formed within a network (Cresswell et al., 2010). This approach has attained special stature in social studies due to its focus on non-human actors and how they impact the social process. It helps in understanding how association among different actors contribute to creation of certain social effects such as power. It takes into consideration how actors are enrolled in a network, how these actors combine to form a whole network and achieve its stability. It can also assist in identifying the

barriers during implementation of new program, technology, or policy. Besides these conceptual benefits, this approach can also aid in practical ways. ANT can act as a roadmap, guiding the researcher to explore the potential areas by framing appropriate research questions (Cresswell et al., 2010).

ANT will help in understanding how both human and non-human actors contribute equally to form information networks. E-Governance as a phenomenon establishes a link between technology and human resources. ANT as an analytical framework helps to study this interrelatedness between non-human (technology) and human actors. ANT significantly emphasizes that the network of social, technical, and physical actors involves a series of transformations, transductions, and translations such that change occurs (Ayyad, 2009). ANT helps us analyse the website as an interplay between various elements, like information technology, citizens, government employees, business associates, and the surrounding environment and brings transformation in how the interaction happens among them. E-Governance can be seen as an association of heterogeneous elements, which makes ANT an appropriate approach to study it. ANT emphasizes that there is no hard boundary between inner and outside domain or natural and social world. The world is in always-entangled state, and it is futile to break them apart in different divisions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The qualitative approach was used to gather the data to empirically show how the identities are constructed. The semi-structured and unstructured interviews along with focus group discussions were used to generate rich data based on the real-time accounts of the users. The SAI structure is divided into three tiers, which include headquarters, regional centres, and sub-regional centres, which further include National Centre of Excellence (NCOE) and SAI Training Centre (STC). An effort was made to include all three tiers, so the study was started with headquarters in New Delhi, and then North Regional Centre, Sonipat was covered, and after that focus was on NCOEs and STCs in Haryana. The focus was Haryana because it is the state, which begs most medals in any international games. So, it is expected that the sports culture and administration of Haryana produce talented sportspersons. The interviews were conducted with administrators (17), coaches (25), and players (20 in-depth interviews & 6 focus group interviews) from SAI. The purpose of the interviews was to get better clarity on the usage of website by different actors and to explore if they face any challenges. The interviews were transcribed and it was found that some gaps were left unanswered so follow-up questions were again asked from the concerned actors. The interviews were complemented by observation of day-to-day usage of the website by the different actors. ANT further provided a critical lens to observe this process.

Online Identity of Sai through Ant Perspective

Cantoni and Tardini (2006) view website as both a technological tool as well as a communication artifact. Therefore, to study different aspects of SAI website ANT approach has been chosen. ANT can help to uncover the semiotics used in website of SAI. There are many signs available on the website that can help create the online identity of SAI, such as

logo, colour, or layout. As discussed earlier, it is problematic to have a hard distinction between offline and online identity. In a similar fashion, ANT also does not believe in fixed boundaries between the social, natural, or technological world (Murdoch, 2005). Therefore, in the case of SAI website, it can be treated as a network built of various social and technological actors (Mitev, 2009). The website of SAI is created by an amalgamation of various actors like administrators, users, internet, software, etc. whose agenda is to provide online sports-related services to interested stakeholders. Website can be seen as a hybrid entity. If an actor fails in this hybrid, entity it may lead to the failure of whole network. For example- one of the actors involved is availability of internet and if it is not there, one cannot access the website and whole network of website collapses.

Due to its networked nature, website can also be called as system, or perfectly an information system, as it includes actors like people, hardware, software, rules, data, etc. working together to collect, process and display information (Tatnall et al., 2002). ANT can help us understand how the identity is being created as it focuses on processes and flows rather than on a particular actor or network. Identities go through constant translation to adapt to the network requirements (Barry, 2006; Singleton, 1995; Thompson, 2003). To translate means to displace, to transform, and to speak for someone else (Latour, 2005; Lindqvist, 2010). Thus, the identity of SAI website needs to be changed as per the requirements of the involved actors like sportsperson, businesses. Thus, a process of translation takes place, as explained earlier, it is a complex process of negotiations and calculations by which an actor is enrolled in a network and speaks in the desired manner. A website builds trust and relationships with its users to translate them and speak on their behalf.

During my fieldwork, I observed the interaction of players and coaches with the website of SAI is minimal. A wrestling player in the North Regional Centre of SAI, Sonipat said that the main source of receiving any information was their coaches. Another player from boxing, SAI Training Centre, Hisar, claimed that 'on the website, the information regarding a camp is uploaded late or sometimes it is not uploaded at all'. So, it is a futile practice to indulge in retaining information from the website. To successfully disseminate information to various actors, a website should have become an obligatory passage point through which every actor must pass. But it failed to do so. As clearly visible from the above remarks from the players. They don't need the website to access the information rather they depend upon the coaches.

In this case, we can identify two main actors, first are users, which consist of coaches, players, and administrators of regional and sub-regional centres, whereas, the other category of actors include developers or coordinators. The coordinators are responsible for the maintenance of the website, which includes the administrators from the headquarters, especially from the IT division. For the coordinators, the aim of the website is clear it should clearly showcase the organizational information, current notices, annual reports, and recent achievements. During the fieldwork, Khelo India Games were ongoing, so the IT department was busy uploading the schedule of the tournament, and players' achievements on the website. When enquired why you do so, one of the administrators replied that 'it is their job to do so'. One of the high rank officials in headquarters when asked about the same replied that 'it is important to showcase

our achievements so that public trust remains with us.’ Apart from the coordinators, users when asked about their experience of using the website, one of the coaches replied that ‘I hardly use the website except for one reason, i.e., to access any job opportunities, because I have many players around me who keeps on asking if there are any job opportunities’. Administrators from the regional and sub-regional centre said that they don’t use the website but they access other e-governance initiatives taken by SAI, such as eOffice, National Sports Repository System (NSRS), etc. Thus to enrol more users, website coordinators have tried to encompass various other features into the website such as Stadia booking facility is provided through website. Even businesses now can access the tender through online means using the website. This creates new avenues to enroll non-users and make their interest align with the interest of the coordinators. Actors like players are more distant from website so efforts are made to enroll them into the network by providing links on the main website to the Right to Information (RTI) website, Khelo India Dashboard, and timely updates of the selection list for various games.

These efforts if successful will lead to the mobilization of the website changing the interaction pattern among various actors, which ultimately causes the translation of the identities of the users as well as the organization. The SAI created its online presence through the website by aligning the interests of other actors to use the resources on its website by making itself the crucial point that every actor must pass through. This process of creating identities is still going on and will shape itself as per the changes introduced by the web coordinators whom themselves get influenced by the users.

CONCLUSION

The focus of this paper was on the role of website and how it creates the online identity for its user and the organization itself. SAI website provides various information pertaining to its functioning and various facilities available with it. SAI is trying to have a stronger online presence; therefore, it revamped its website in July 2021. Actor Network Theory (ANT) has been chosen to study this phenomenon of online identity creation because it treats social and technological actors at par. This theory believes in principle of generalized symmetry and free association. With help of this approach, website is treated as a network and focus has been laid on the process through which SAI achieves its online identity.

Notes

- 1) The data has been retrieved from <https://data.un.org/en/iso/in.html> on September 27, 2021.
- 2) Information received through RTI filed against SAI (RTI No. SAOIN/R/E/21/00158 filed on 22-06-2021).
- 3) Information received through RTI filed against SAI (RTI No. SAOIN/R/E/21/00158 filed on 22-06-2021).

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